

The System of Administrative Services at Level of Territorial Communities: Dynamics of Development (2009-2019 years)

*Tetiana Serohina*¹

¹ Dnipropetrovsk Regional Institute for Public Administration, National Academy for Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, Management and Project Management Department, Gogol str., 29, 49044 Dnipro, Ukraine

Abstract. The article describes the dynamic of the Administrative Service Centres (ASC) network development in Ukraine from 2009 to 2019. The reform of administrative services is one of the most systematic and consistent in Ukraine due to the consistent implementation of a set of state measures and the expansion of the role of international technical assistance projects. Studies of the quality of administrative services confirm the positive changes. Analysis of the growth dynamics of the ASC number showed that this process is heterogeneous, with almost no centers being created until 2012, and in 2013 and 2014 (457 and 111 ASC, respectively) this process was most active. From 2015 to 2019, the growth of ASC was slower, and no centers were established in 1 quarter 2020. Recent trends suggest that, at the current stage of decentralization, the existing network is able to provide citizens with proper administrative services. The main focus of the experts is on solving the problematic issues that arise in the existing centers. Such problems include the existence of "formal" ASC when there is no systematic vision for the appointment of the center, ASC of district state administrations, in the period when the latter is planned to be eliminated in the near future, obstacles to the decentralization of services (services of registration of civil acts, registration of vehicles, etc.), require special attention.

1 Introduction

The decentralization of authority today is a defining direction of public policy, which requires special attention in the context of the development of the public service delivery system. This is due in the first place to the fact that the processes that accompany this reform cause significant changes in the system under study. Therefore, the redistribution of powers between different levels of government creates new opportunities for improvement of the public service delivery system, facilitates the implementation of new approaches based on the principle of subsidiarity. To date, there is considerable experience in providing local governments with quality administrative services. However, their potential has not been fully realized to date.

Accordingly, government policy is also expected to have a consistent, prudent approach on the one hand, and an opportunity to respond promptly to the challenges and issues that inevitably accompany any reform. In the context of the issue under study, the impact of decentralization processes on the system of administrative services provision and the formation of the ASC network deserves special attention.

20 November 2020

It should be noted that in a number of reforms aimed at improving the public service delivery system, the reform of administrative services is one of the most systematic and consistent [11]. This is the result of the implementation of a set of state measures on the one hand, and the extension of the role of international technical assistance projects on the other.

In general, the creation of a ASC network is one of the leading areas for reforming the administrative service delivery system. The implementation of this direction has justified itself, as evidenced by research data on the work and quality of administrative services.

According to the data, if in 2015, 82% of respondents rated positively the overall evaluation of the ASC's work, and negatively 5%, then in 2019 it was positive - 90.9%, negatively - 2%. To receive the service, citizens had to make one or two visits - 55% and 32% respectively. 30% of visitors said that they did not have to wait in line, and 27% of respondents said that the waiting time did not exceed 10 minutes. Significantly changed indicators of the quality of administrative services - if in 2014 a very good rating was given by 5% of respondents, in 2019 - 19%, a negative assessment in 2014 was delivered by 32% of visitors, and in 2019 - 16 % [11].

2 Data and Methods

The analysis of the administrative services system was conducted on the basis of legal acts and the results of expert studies collected by public authorities and international technical assistance programs. In particular, the Ministry of Communities and Territories of Ukraine monitors the process of decentralization of power and the reform of local self-government on a monthly basis [3], which contains data on the creation of united territorial communities, decentralization of power and public services.

The information on the quality of administrative services, which allowed to establish the dynamics of change, was presented by the Expert Monitoring Center in the 30 largest cities and 20 OTGs [4], conducted by experts of the network of analytical centers of Ukraine UPLAN [12]. Analytical of quality of administrative services provided by Ilko Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation [2].

3 Presentation of the main results

Current world trends in the system of public administration cause changes in existing and formation of fundamentally new approaches to the system of public service delivery in Ukraine, which is based on the introduction of "a new ideology of functioning of the executive power and local self-government as an activity to ensure the realization of citizens' rights and freedoms" [6].

It should be noted that in a number of reforms aimed at improving the public service delivery system, the reform of administrative services is one of the most systematic and consistent [11]. This is the result of the implementation of a set of state measures on the one hand, and the extension of the role of international technical assistance projects on the other. In particular, the focus of the U-LEAD Program with Europe is on the process of building a ASC network in Ukraine.

In general, the creation of a ASC network is one of the leading areas for reforming the administrative service delivery system. The implementation of this direction has justified itself, as evidenced by research data on the work and quality of administrative services. One such study was conducted by the Ilko Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation [11]. As part of this study, Expert monitoring of ASC in the 30 largest cities and 20 amalgamated territorial communities, Consumer survey of quality of service provision in ASC in 30 largest cities, and National Sociological Survey on the quality of service delivery at ASC.

20 November 2020

The ASC network, as one of the key drivers of reform performance, requires particular attention in the context of the study. Therefore, we will place the data on the number of generated ASC's in the table by years (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of growth of the number of ASC's in Ukraine by years (according to the Monitoring of the process of decentralization of power and reform of local self-government [3])

Year	New ASCs have been created	The total number of ASCs	The total number of ASCs in the ATC	The relative number of ASCs in the ATC
2009	-	1		
2010	2	3		
2011	5	8		
2012	37	45		
2013	457	502		
2014	111	613		
2015	22	635	< 10	< 1,5 %
2016	47	682	23	3,4 %
2017	64	746	71	9,5 %
2018	32	778	125	16 %
2019	28	806	176	22 %
2020 (I quarter)	-	806	176	22 %

Based on the above data, it can be noted that the processes of improving the administrative service delivery system by 2012 were slow enough, successful practices were rather an exception to the general picture (Municipal Services Center in Berdyansk (2004) [1], Transparent Office in Vinnitsa (2008) [8], etc.).

The real prerequisites for reforming the administrative services sector as a whole and building the network of ASCs, in particular, were provided with an appropriate legal framework. One of the key documents was the Law of Ukraine "On Administrative Services", adopted in 2012, which focused on the formation of ASCs. Therefore, since 2013, there has been a tendency for a sharp increase in the number of ASCs (457 and 111 in 2013 and 2014, respectively), although from the outset their creation was not always provided at the proper level.

After the unprecedented increase in the number of ASCs in 2013 - 2014, the pace of their creation slowed down considerably (from 22 in 2015 to 64 in 2019), no centres were created in the first quarter of 2020. This suggests that in the context of current decentralization processes, when the first stage of administrative-territorial reform, related to the voluntary association of territorial communities (1009 amalgamated territorial communities - as of March 2020 [3]), the growth of the number of ASCs stopped.

However, the conditionality of the processes of reforming the sphere of administrative services provision by the processes of decentralization is not only influenced by the dynamics of growth of the number of ASCs. The cornerstone is the fact that most administrative service centres have been set up by district state administrations, which, according to registered draft laws ("On the Principles of Administrative and Territorial System of Ukraine" [7], etc.), must be liquidated by March 1, 2021. At the same time, as of March 2020, out of 806 ASCs, 435 were created by district state administrations and only 22% (176) of CNAPs were created by amalgamated territorial communities [3].

In order to ensure consistency in the reform process, a Decree of the President of Ukraine "On Some Measures to Provide Quality Public Services" was released on

20 November 2020

September 4, 2019. The Decree refers to the further abolition of the “obligation to establish administrative service centers under district state administrations” [5].

Today there are several variants of ASC functioning - those created:

- district state administrations;
- local self-government bodies (city councils of cities of rayon / regional importance / regional centers and Kyiv City Council, village, settlement councils);
- district state administrations and local self-government bodies - so-called. city-district ASC (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Distribution of ASC

Fig. 4 The distribution of the main sources of information on ASC

Overall estimates of ASC performance were good in previous evaluations. But this time they have improved. Thus, if in 2015 82% of respondents evaluated the work of such bodies positively, and 5% negatively, then in 2019 the share of those who considered the work of the CNAP good - 90.9%, and those who rated it as bad - 2% (Fig. 2).

Therefore, the state policy on providing citizens with administrative services in the next stages of administrative-territorial reform, including those related to the liquidation of district state administrations, deserves special attention. Such a policy should be based on the principles [10]: ensuring access of persons to administrative services; preservation of the existing ASC infrastructure; retention of ASC staff.

Fig. 2 Evaluation of the ASC

Fig. 3 Employee friendliness

Compared to 2015, the level of satisfaction of citizens with the friendliness and competence of ASC employees has also increased. Thus, in 2015, 92% of visitors were satisfied with the friendliness of ASC employees and 9% were dissatisfied, and in 2019 95.9% were satisfied with the friendliness of ASC employees and 4.1% were dissatisfied, respectively (see Fig. 2). The level of competence of ASC employees was satisfied by 91%, dissatisfied - 9%, and in 2019 - 95% and 5% respectively (see Fig. 3).

20 November 2020

In all cities, the overwhelming majority of those who applied to the ASC rate his work well. Most of the absolute positive ratings ("very good") from the citizens who applied to the ASC (who at the same time have the proper level of service integration) were obtained by the ASC in Vinnitsa (84%), Chernivtsi (85%), Ivano-Frankivsk (76%) , Kyiv (76%), Lutsk (76%), Rivne (75%) [10].

The overwhelming majority of respondents to the survey asked the ASC to get a specific service - 78.5%, while 21.5% visited all cities for information and consultation. At the same time, most of the surveyed users of services (71%) were able to fully resolve the issue they addressed, another 23% said that the issue was not resolved, but is in the process of resolution. To obtain administrative services, on average, all the surveyed ASC citizens had only one or two visits - 55% and 32% respectively [10].

In the vast majority of ASC visitors are satisfied with the informative signage at the entrance to the premises and the presence of other signs; availability of stands with information, sample documents; availability of information cards of services; availability of forms, forms; arrangement of waiting places; the general condition of the premises and the mode of operation of the body. The main positive aspects of receiving administrative services for the respondents were as follows: officials acted correctly and politely; a clear explanation of all the circumstances of the case, including what documents are required, etc., as well as the premises of the authority, sufficient information was needed to obtain the service and samples for filling in documents, and comfortable and comfortable waiting conditions (chairs, places for filling in documents, etc.) were provided.

The main complaints primarily relate to the large queues (20%), the length of the case and the lack of explanations as to what documents were required, so man has to go several times. However, the major problem - the big queues - became less mentioned compared to past polls (down from 42% to 20%). Comparing the dynamics of the "negative elements" from personal experience of receiving administrative services, it is worth noting that in all indicators, comparing the data of December 2014 and July 2019, there is a very positive trend. This applies in particular to queues (from 42% reduction to 20%), room comfort (reduction of complaints from 16% to 6%), conditions for persons with disabilities and parents with children (from 9% to 4%), bribe solicitation (from 5% reduction to 2%), rude behavior of officials (from 16% reduction to 4%), refusal without explanation (from 4% reduction to 2%), did not explain what documents were needed (reduction from 30% to 11%), absence necessary information (from 14% reduction to 6%), the case took too long (reduction from 28% to 12%), walking in different instances (reduction from 20% to 8%), requesting unforeseen documents (reduction from 11% to 4%), purchase of forms and "paid additional services" (from 19% reduction to 5%) [10].

Compared to 2015, awareness of the activities of state or local authorities in the field of administrative services has increased significantly. Thus, 42% are aware of the creation of administrative service centers (25%). A third of the population knows nothing about any actions (half did not know anything before). Increasing awareness is also associated with an increase in the number of ASCs. Thus, 46% of the respondents said that in their city a ASC was formed, in 2015 there were 20%, and in 2014 - only 13%. At the same time, the number of people who applied to the ASC also increased, making up 43% of those who know about the ASC in their city. In 2013, this figure was 35% [10].

The level of satisfaction with ASC services by their direct users is quite high. Thus, 82% are satisfied with the services received at ASC, and just over 10% are dissatisfied. 5% of the population have already used online administrative services. The most frequently used services are of the Ministry of Social Policy, which is associated with a large number of requests for social services.

20 November 2020

Integration of services is increasing, but the level of integration of services with “foreign” passports and “internal” passports in the form of a card is uneven. These services are provided in 77% of the surveyed urban CNAPs and 45% of CNAPs in the CTV. Particularly negative was the fact that at the time of monitoring the provision of “passport” services was not ensured in the ASC of 7 cities - regional centers (Zhytomyr, Zaporizhia, Kramatorsk, Kropyvnytskyi, Severodonetsk, Kherson, Uzhgorod). Photo passport service in the form of a booklet (25/45 years old) is available only in 67% of the investigated urban ASCs and in 70% of the ASCs in the ATC. 97% of ASCs in cities and 85% of ASCs in ATCs provide services for issuing information on SCCs and land registration. The most problematic for integration into the ASC are new service groups, in particular, social and pension spheres, registration of civil acts, vehicle registration and driver's license. At the same time, a higher level of integration of social services (65%) and pension services (60%) is demonstrated by the ASC in ATC. In urban ASCs, these figures are much lower and are 47% and 23% respectively. Obviously, due to the mass nature of these services, it is still easier to integrate them into smaller communities [10].

The process of improving the administrative service delivery system is ongoing. In settlements (communities) with different status, different models of CNAP are implemented, which is caused by different set of powers.

Therefore, the state policy on providing citizens with administrative services in the next stages of administrative-territorial reform, including those related to the liquidation of district state administrations, deserves special attention. After all, as we can see in fig. 1, most of the ASCs were created by district state administrations 435 out of 806 (see Fig. 1).

3 Conclusions

At the present stage of improving the administrative service delivery system, special attention is paid to the development of the ASC network. It is important in the process of transition from the first stage of decentralization of voluntary community association to the second, not only to ensure accessibility and quality of administrative services at the achieved level, to maintain staffing and material resources, but also to promote its further development.

References

1. Berdyansk City Council. Official site. Available at: <https://bmr.gov.ua/index.php?id=800001134> [in Ukrainian]
2. Dynamics of change in the quality of administrative services in Ukraine. Available at: <https://www.pravo.org.ua/img/zstored/files> [in Ukrainian]
3. Monitoring the decentralization process and reforming local self-government. Available at: <https://decentralization.gov.ua/mainmonitoring> [in Ukrainian]
4. Assessment of ASC of the 30 largest cities in Ukraine. Available at: <https://www.pravo.org.ua/img/zstored/files> [in Ukrainian]
5. On some measures to ensure the provision of quality public services: Presidential Decree of September 4, 2019. Available at: <https://www.president.gov.ua/documents/6472019-29441> [in Ukrainian]
6. On Measures to Implement the Concept of Administrative Reform in Ukraine: Presidential Decree of July 22 1998 No. 810/98. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/810/98> [in Ukrainian]
7. Transparent office of Vinnytsia city council. Available at: <https://transparent.vmr.gov.ua/default.aspx> [in Ukrainian]
8. Proposals of the U-LEAD with Europe program on public policy on administrative services. February 2020. Available at: <https://tsnap.ulead.org.ua/wp->

20 November 2020

content/uploads/2020/02/White-Book_web-2.pdf [in Ukrainian]

9. Proposals for the elimination of the ASC of the district state administrations of the U-LEAD Program with Europe. Available at: <https://tsnap.ulead.org.ua/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Analiz-polityky-shhodo-TSNAP-RDA.pdf> [in Ukrainian]

10. Quality of administrative service delivery in Ukraine: citizens' opinion, expert evaluation and changes over 5 years. Ilko Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation. Sep. 4 2019. – Available at: <https://dif.org.ua/article/yakist-nadannya-administrativnikh-poslug-v-ukraini-dumka-gromadyan-otsinka-fakhivtsiv-ta-zmini-za-5-rokiv> [in Ukrainian]

11. UPLAN. URL : <https://uplan.org.ua/about/>